

ANALYTICAL AND NUMERICAL STUDIES INTO THE VACUUM INFUSION PROCESS: IN-PLANE FLOW IN COMPRESSIBLE POROUS MEDIA.

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ABSTRACT

Vacuum infusion (VI) and Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) are among the most significant and widely used Liquid Composite Manufacturing processes. Both rely on resin infusion of dry reinforcement materials inside closed moulds but are fundamentally different in terms of mould construction and fluid pressures used. Unlike RTM, vacuum infusion (also known with slight variations as VARTM, SCRIMP™, VM, RIFT, etc.), is commonly used to produce large components and is acknowledged for its relative low cost and superior quality when compared with traditional open mould techniques. Furthermore, the use of a flexible polymeric film in VI has profound implications in the fluid mechanics of the process. This flexibility of the vacuum bag is responsible for a fluid pressure dependent compaction of the reinforcement and consequently local time dependent thickness and permeability.

VI has been the object of intensive study in the past decade; nonetheless a number of problems still need to be addressed such as further analytical developments of the flow model, identification of relevant parameters, and sensitivity studies.

This work's main contribution is then to explore these issues and reveal the implication of different fibre architectures, compaction and permeability models and parameters on flow and mould filling. The parametric studies are also focused on the modelling of natural permeability variations for control oriented applications of this model.

KEYWORDS: Vacuum infusion, Analytical modelling, Numerical analysis, Consolidation, Resin flow

INTRODUCTION

Liquid composite moulding (LCM) processes such as resin transfer moulding RTM and vacuum infusion (VI) constitute one of the most significant families of composite production techniques. The different LCM processes are complementary in terms of component size, number and cost. Due to mould stiffness and cost issues, RTM is generally used to produce components of a limited size but, as a faster production technique using robust moulds this process is synonymous with high production volumes. The slower VI does not have the high cost and size limitations of RTM but it cannot easily be used for large series of components due to lower processing pressures and necessary changes in ancillary materials.

The differences between these two processes are also observable in terms of component properties. RTM components often have high surface quality on all faces and small design tolerances while VI components present a more challenging set of characteristics such as variable thickness, volume fraction (and, consequently, mechanical properties), low quality on one of the faces and local resin content and mass dependent on fluid pressure. Furthermore, the material costs associated with the large structures which characterize VI often involve a high financial risk and rely significantly on the expertise of the workshop personnel. This experience based approach is complemented with RTM flow studies which, while

valuable, do not explore the aforementioned parameters in VI and therefore cannot predict final component weight, dimensions and mechanical properties.

Not only are the output properties of these processes different, they are directly influenced by preform properties and mould/gate design. Due to its flow dependent cavity thickness, VI experiences a higher degree of variability than that observed in RTM. One significant source of property variations is the reinforcement permeability which, as Pan *et al* [1] and Hoes *et al* [2] described, is not a constant value but follows a normal distribution. Consequently, flow in VI, as well as RTM, does not follow exactly the ideal case but presents variations due to the statistical distribution of the flow properties of the preform.

Generally, as is shown in Figure 1, VI employs a single die, where the reinforcement and at times a flow enhancing media are laid. A membrane, which is sealed onto the mould, closes the cavity. Air is extracted from the cavity and the atmospheric pressure outside the bag compresses the reinforcement onto the mould.

Figure 1 - VI mold assembly: 1 – vacuum seal, 2 – vacuum bag, 3 – distribution media, 4 – peel ply, 5 – reinforcement, 6 – inlet, 7 – mould, 8 – outlet.

Figure 2 - Effect of fluid pressure on compaction in VI

When the inlet is opened, the differential between atmospheric pressure outside and the vacuum inside forces the thermosetting resin into the mould, filling the cavity. Compared with RTM's fully enclosing stiff mould, the use of a flexible vacuum bag implies that the fluid pressure field affects the fibre bed compaction, as is shown in Figure 2. Clearly, time-dependent compaction also implies that permeability and porosity values become variable which will in turn affect flow.

In the course of this paper, the study of the fluid mechanics of VI considers flow through a compressing medium: the same fluid pressure field that induces flow in VI also modifies the local compaction state of the reinforcement and imposes a time dependence on permeability, porosity and thickness. As fluid pressure changes due to the movement of the flow front, so does the compaction pressure on the reinforcement which introduces time dependence in these properties. This is illustrated in Figure 2.

In order to understand the vacuum infusion process, its variables and their correlation as well as the influence of variability on component quality and production robustness, several modelling approaches were explored. Beginning with the 1D analytical form of the flow model, the present paper will discuss the implications of several material properties on the component output of VI. A 2D finite element control volume model of VI based on the University of Delaware's flow modelling tool LIMS is also discussed and an application of the FE-CV model to variable flow properties is shown.

BACKGROUND

Flow in consolidating media plays an important role in branches of engineering such as material sciences, petroleum industry, chemical engineering and soil mechanics, among others. Composite manufacturing is a recent extension to the variety of problems tackled. Much of the relevant early background literature predates the use of VI as it is known today.

Hydrological flow in consolidating soil was initially discussed by Biot in 1941 [3]. Hydrology is primarily concerned with saturated diffusivity studies, i.e. pore water movement in consolidating saturated soil and deformation of a saturated porous mass. Major hydrological theories on flow through compacting media assume non-coupled permeability and fluid pressure (Scheidegger [4]). More recent consolidation research (de Boer [5]) still makes assumptions such as uniform compaction pressure. Nevertheless, hydrological theories have been adapted to composites manufacturing by Gebart [6] and Gutowski [7]-[9].

Gutowski et al. were among the first authors to study consolidation of composites [7]-[9] but their studies focused on manufacturing techniques such as compression moulding in a two-part rigid mould. Thickness, although time-dependent, is independently controlled. Hammami et al. [10]-[11] modelled the vacuum infusion process focusing on 1D flow with the same governing equations as Gutowski but allowing for local variations of thickness. The one dimensional compressible medium flow case along x where the control volume is defined over the whole thickness h of the laminate can be shown to lead to the following governing equation:

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = - \frac{\partial(u.h)}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

Despite the fact that different algebraic forms of equation (1) are suggested by Gutowski *et al.* [7] and Hammami *et al.* [10], both are identical and represent the same approach. Han *et al.* [12] use a different approach which is based on developments presented by Scheidegger [4]. Nevertheless, the following discussion will use the Gutowski-Hammami continuity equation as the foundation for further analytical developments.

Compaction: Reinforcement compaction differentiates VI from RTM. The variable thickness has quantifiable implications on permeability, porosity and flow. The thickness is clearly dependent on position, in this case distance from inlet, showing the effect of local fluid pressure and preform compressibility.

Compaction of composite preforms was studied experimentally and analytically by several research groups. Studies such as those of Chen *et al.* for single layer woven materials [13] or multilayer with nesting effects [14] are good analytical examples. However, experimental models such as those of Gutowski *et al.* [7]-[8] are easier to use in parametric studies or models. Assuming a quasi-static compaction, their model is expressed as:

$$P_{comp} = A_s \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\frac{v_f}{v_0}} - 1}{\left(\sqrt{\frac{v_{fA}}{v_f}} - 1 \right)^4} \quad (2)$$

where P_{comp} and v_f are respectively the compaction pressure which is exerted on the reinforcement and the resulting fibre volume fraction. Note that for VI P_{comp} is the local difference between the atmospheric and fluid pressures. The remaining variables A_s , v_0 and v_a represent the reinforcement's spring constant, the

volume fraction at zero compaction pressure and the theoretical maximum volume fraction, which all depend on reinforcement architecture. In reality A_s and v_a must either be estimated or determined experimentally.

Another empirical approach, reported by Robitaille *et al.* [15]-[17], used a power law fit to relate compaction pressure to fibre volume fraction. Assuming quasi-static compaction, their model takes the following form:

$$v_f = v_{f0} \cdot P_{comp}^B \quad (3)$$

where v_{f0} is the fibre volume fraction at 1 Pa and B is the stiffening index, which depends on fibre architecture. Due to fibre lubrication, dry and saturated compaction behaviours are different. Given that v_{f0} and B apply to the saturated part of the preform, data should be obtained in saturated compaction experiments. This difference in compaction properties between dry and wet reinforcement is experimentally observed at the fluid flow front. There is often a first phase of thickness reduction due to fibre lubrication (which increases compliance) and a subsequent phase of expansion due to the reduction of compaction pressure. The larger dry thickness does not, however, affect flow. Flow front thickness evolves as a function of saturation but the overall hydraulic resistance to flow is a function of wet permeability and porosity alone.

Preform thickness is a function of volume fraction. Using the surface density of the reinforcement $\rho_{surface}$ and the bulk fibre density ρ (for glass 2540 kg/m³), equation (4) can be used to obtain thickness as a function of pressure:

$$h = \frac{\rho_{surface}}{\rho \cdot v_{f0} \cdot P_{comp}^B} \quad (4)$$

Permeability: Originally designed for flow through spherical particles, the Kozeny-Carman model of permeability (5) has been verified extensively for certain types of porous media and applied with reasonable success to woven or aligned fibres [4], [7]:

$$K = k \cdot \frac{(1 - v_f)^3}{v_f^2} \quad (5)$$

The value of the Kozeny constant, k , is usually determined experimentally and reflects the geometry of the reinforcement. Note that fibre volume fraction is a function of compaction pressure, and so is permeability.

An alternative approach, suggested by Rudd *et al.* [18], is based on the modelling of UD fibre bed properties, as suggested by Gebart [6], and subsequent association of different layers of UD fibres into laminate properties. As suggested by Brusckhe *et al.* [19] equation (5) does not model permeability with complete accuracy but nevertheless, the Kozeny-Carman equation is used in here for simplicity.

Numerical simulation tools: All numerical research presented here was conducted using LIMS: liquid injection moulding simulation, developed at the University of Delaware Center for Composite Materials. LIMS can be described as a dedicated finite element / control volume based simulation of flow through porous media, capable of analysing both 2D and 3D flows. LIMS 5.0 has a built in scripting language, LBASIC, which was added so that boundary conditions could be modified during the simulation [20]-[21]. As is the case with other FE based simulation packages, it is necessary to supply a meshed geometry, permeabilities, porosities and boundary conditions to carry out the simulations [22].

ANALYTICAL MODELLING

In-plane flow through a porous medium can be modelled using Darcy's law, which for one dimensional flow in the x-direction gives fluid velocity (u_x) as:

$$u_x = -\frac{K}{\mu} \frac{dP}{dx} \quad (6)$$

where K is the reinforcement permeability, μ is the fluid viscosity, and P is the fluid pressure. Following the analysis of Gutowski et al [9] the continuity equation for one-dimensional in-plane flow in a compacting porous medium is given in equation (1). This expression differs from that used for flow in an incompressible medium (eg. RTM). Combining equations (1) and (6) for a constant viscosity fluid:

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\mu} \cdot \left[\left(K \cdot \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + h \cdot \frac{\partial K}{\partial x} \right) \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + h \cdot K \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} \right) \right] \quad (7)$$

Since both thickness and permeability are functions of pressure, which is a function of position in the mould x ($h [P (x)]$ and $K [P (x)]$) equation (3) can be recast as:

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\mu} \cdot \left[\left(K \cdot \frac{\partial h}{\partial P} + h \cdot \frac{\partial K}{\partial P} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \right)^2 + h \cdot K \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} \right) \right] \quad (8)$$

A characteristic of the pressure field solution in VI arises from equation (8), which does not feature partial derivatives of h and K with respect to x . Pressure remains constant if it is calculated not at the position x of a point inside the flow but at its relative location between the inlet and the flow front. For example, pressure is constant midway between the inlet and the outlet, even though the physical location of the mid-point changes at each moment. This stems from the fact that permeability K is a function of thickness h . The 1D fluid pressure field can therefore be solved once and scaled with flow front movement. Mathematically this is achieved by performing a variable substitution $\alpha = x/L$ where L is the instantaneous flow front position. In this α -referential, the flow front is located at $\alpha = 1$ while the inlet is at $\alpha = 0$ regardless of time. Assuming that one can ignore rate effects, equation (8) can be developed to:

$$-\left[\left(\frac{1}{h} - \frac{\alpha}{[h]_{\alpha=1}} \right) \cdot \frac{dh}{dP} + \frac{1}{K} \frac{dK}{dP} \right] \left(\frac{dP}{d\alpha} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{d^2 P}{d\alpha^2} \right) \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) can be solved using an iterative finite difference solution to compute the pressure field, from which flow front progression can be determined using Darcy's law.

ANALYTICAL MODELLING RESULTS

Solutions of the fluid pressure field described in the above section were obtained with an iterative finite difference (FD) scheme. Iteration is needed to resolve the coupling between permeability, fibre volume fraction and local fluid pressure. Table 1 shows the modelling data used to obtain fluid pressure fields for a representative range of materials. The same values are used in all simulations as both the Kozeny constant k and the surface density $\rho_{surface}$ cancel out in governing equation (9). Compaction properties are presented in Table 2.

The curved profiles of the fluid pressure fields in Figure 3 are due to an increase in compaction from inlet to outlet as predicted by equation (9). Conversely, permeability decreases in the same direction. To overcome this increasing resistance, the local fluid pressure gradient increases from the inlet to the outlet. In the incompressible case resistance is constant and so is the pressure gradient.

Modeling data		
No. of nodes		100
Convergence criterion		1.00E-06
Outlet pressure (absolute)		0 atm
Inlet pressure (absolute)		0.9 atm
Surface density	ρ_{Surface}	1 Kg/m ²
Bulk density of glass	ρ	2540 Kg/m ³
Kozeny constant	k	5.00E-11 Kg/m ³
Resin viscosity	μ	0.2 Pa.s

Table 1 - Input data for fluid pressure field solution

Material	Type and layer no.	V_{f0} (%)	B
Vetrotex U812	Random mat.	3	0.50
		6	0.54
Vetrotex U101	Random mat.	3	2.09
		6	1.85
NCS 81053	Stich. Bidirect.	3	6.78
		6	11.0
EBX 936	Stich. bidirect.	3	13.3
		6	16.8
		12	18.5

Table 2 - Compaction model data. Based on Robitaille *et al.* [15], [16] and [17]

Increased compressibility results in a larger departure from the linear case. Since reinforcement compressibility decreases with increasing initial fibre volume fraction v_{f0} and density of fibre packing, higher v_{f0} materials such as NCS 81053 show a more linear fluid pressure field. This can also be observed in Figure 4 where nesting increases the initial fibre volume fraction, resulting in a more linear fluid pressure field.

Figure 3 - Fluid pressure field comparison for 6 layers of NCS81053, U101 and U812

Figure 4 - Influence of nesting in the fluid pressure field of 3 and 6 layers of NCS 81053

Inlet and outlet pressure levels are also determinant factors in the curvature of the fluid pressure field. Figure 5 shows the change in fluid pressure field curvature for three cases: 1) from 1 to 0 atm absolute, 2) from 1 to 0.85 atm abs, 3) from 0.15 to 0 atm abs.

In the first case compaction varies substantially from inlet to outlet and the fluid pressure field is highly non-linear. In the second case the material is subjected to low compaction pressures which result in a moderate variation in compaction. Accordingly the fluid pressure field shows a more linear behaviour. In the third case the material is subjected to higher compaction pressures which result in nearly homogeneous compaction of the preform. Whilst the pressure difference is identical in the second and third cases the fluid pressure field is now almost linear.

The combination of fluid pressure field and compaction determines the distributions of fibre volume fraction and thickness at any point in time. Thickness data, such as shown in Figure 6, can be used to predict resin consumption and to predict local mechanical properties. In this case the thickness is shown as a function of surface density, i.e. Figure 6 reflects the trend, in $mm / (kg / m^2)$, of the laminate thickness while its final value will depend on the number of layers and the reinforcement architecture. The experimental validation of these developments can be found in [24].

Figure 5 – Effect of outlet pressure settings on the fluid pressure field of U812

Figure 6 – Thickness and volume fraction as a function of location in NCS 81053

GENERAL SOLUTION OF VI USING LIMS

The use of an established RTM software (LIMS) was preferred over the development of a stand alone VI numerical simulation due to, in essence, the long development time that would be necessary to produce a proven software package. In fact, due to the extensive research that has gone in to the development of many of the present RTM simulation packages it would not be possible to reach the same level of sophistication rapidly.

One of the main advantages LIMS presents over other packages is its extensive scripting capability that allowed the incorporation of reinforcement compaction during filling in VI. In order to simulate VI's flow through a compressible porous medium, the software is required to update thickness, porosity and permeability locally as a function of compaction pressure. This is accomplished through an *LBASIC* script, which is able to apply the required changes and check iteratively for error in these changes by re-solving the pressure field under the new conditions. Each iteration step uses the pressure field which was calculated previously to assign permeability, thickness and porosity values to individual elements. The solution has converged when the pressure field no longer changes significantly (error in pressure field is smaller than the tolerance). At this point the flow front is advanced and the procedure is restarted for a new filling circumstance. A schematic representation of LIMS' *LBASIC* algorithm is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - VI algorithm used in LIMS LBASIC script

Through the use of auxiliary compaction and permeability models the calculation of flow in the compressible medium for cases involving 1D or 2D shell components in LIMS becomes possible. Furthermore, the two proposed methodologies (analytical and numerical) are fundamentally different from each other. The analytical approach solves a stand-alone equation, while the numerical approach involves an independent computation mechanism, which is iterated by a controlling script. Reference [24] describes the comparison between numerical and analytical models and the experimental validation of the proposed algorithm, and shows a maximum relative error between the models of 2.04% (U812, 6 layers).

PREFORM PERMEABILITY DISTRIBUTION

As mentioned above, recent studies of preform permeability ([1]-[2]) show that in reality reinforcement permeability varies due to statistical changes within the fibre architecture. These might be due to

randomness in nesting of fabric layers, or to variations in tow paths within individual layers resulting from fabric manufacture and subsequent handling. For these reasons filling patterns during LCM should be expected to vary between preforms; this of course reflects experience in industry. Useful process models should reflect these variations, by predicting the distribution in possible outcomes from any moulding process. These would provide the range of filling patterns that might be expected, and also fill time and last point to fill (guiding vent or vacuum port location). From this the likelihood of success for any combination of materials and injection strategy could be determined.

To model the effects of permeability variations on flow, predicted or measured distributions in properties can be incorporated within LCM filling simulations. Input files for these simulations are generated automatically by in-house software, with properties for each element generated using a Monte-Carlo method. For textile permeability following a normal distribution, the technique requires the generation of random numbers within the range [0,1], which are used to determine appropriate property values from the cumulative probability distribution function. In this way each element within the model will have a different permeability tensor, but permeabilities over a large number of analyses should conform to the measured normal distribution.

SIMULATION OF REAL-LIFE FLOW

Figure 8 illustrates predicted locations for the last point to be filled in a rectangular mould injected from all four corners, obtained using the LIMS software from the University of Delaware. If permeability were identical for each element, one would expect the last point to fill to be in the centre of the mould. For Figure 8, the measured permeability distribution for a 2x2 twill weave glass fabric at 53% fibre volume fraction was used (mean value of $2.6 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$ and standard deviation of $5.7 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$, from [2]). Clearly there is significant scatter in predicted last points to fill, with results restricted to a relatively narrow band around the vertical centre-line. Figure 9 was obtained using the same procedure but with the standard deviation doubled. Now the scatter is increased significantly, with last point to fill located relatively close to one of the mould corners on a number of occasions.

Figure 8 – Final points filled in a Monte-Carlo study with 5 000 RTM simulations. Four gate injection scheme (corners). K data from [2].

Figure 9 - Same as Figure 8 doubling the standard deviation of permeability.

Unlike the RTM case, where the only parameter in the Monte-Carlo study was permeability, there are a number of variables changing concurrently in VI. The inclusion of a compliant porous medium requires the systematic variation of at least two of these parameters: surface density and Kozeny constant. All others (volume fraction, thickness, and permeability) can be determined using the auxiliary models discussed above. Accordingly, the local values of thickness and volume fraction are a direct function of surface density ($\mu_{\text{surface}} = 8.43 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$ and $\sigma_{\text{surface}} = 0.47 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$, where μ and σ represent the average and standard deviation respectively). The surface density was obtained directly from an equivalent “number of layers” (L) assumed to be characterized statistically by $\mu_L=9$ and $\sigma_L=0.5$. The surface density

value was then used to define the local compaction properties using a linear regression of the EBX 936 data shown in Table 2. Permeability, while linked to the previous variables through applicable compaction and permeability models, was also varied through the introduction of a normally distributed Kozeny constant: $\mu_k = 7.18 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$ and $\sigma_k = 4.36 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$. These values were chosen in order to have the same permeability distribution as the RE144/255 material described in [2]. The distribution of the Kozeny constant was nevertheless connected with the distribution of surface density as the random number used to determine local ρ_{surface} and k was the same.

Using this methodology, the 2D LIMS VI model was used to study a line gate arrangement. The resulting variable permeability, volume fraction and thickness were obtained and are shown in Figures 10, 11 and 12. Note that flow evolves from left (inlet) to right (outlet). As can be observed, these properties are location dependent while simultaneously representing the expected reinforcement variability.

Figure 10 – Evolution of permeability. Iso- K lines: $7.75 \text{ E-}11 \text{ m}^2$ to $2.2 \text{ E-}11 \text{ m}^2$ in 12 divisions.

Figure 11 – Evolution of volume fraction. Iso- v_f lines: 40% to 55% in 16 divisions.

Figure 12 – 3D Thickness distribution (x150). Iso- h lines: 8.5 mm to 5.5 mm in 7 divisions.

CONCLUSIONS

As was shown, VI specific models are required when one intends to study the full impact of preform properties on flow and gating arrangement robustness. With models such as the one proposed, it is foreseeable that VI specific control tools and optimisation techniques could be developed. The full impact of the statistical distribution of permeability on LCM techniques still requires an in-depth study but the introduction of Monte-Carlo techniques on virtual experimentation / process development could have a vast potential.

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